

Diagnostic Value of 3D Transvaginal Ultrasonography in Endometrial Carcinoma among Postmenopausal Women

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Abstract:

Introduction: Endometrial carcinoma typically causes postmenopausal women to experience abnormal vaginal bleeding. Women with suspected endometrial pathology were investigated initially with 3D-TVUSG and later with endometrial biopsy.

Objectives: To assess the diagnostic value of three-dimensional transvaginal ultrasound (3D-TVUSG) for detecting endometrial carcinoma among postmenopausal women.

Methods: A prospective observational study among 61 post-menopausal women was conducted in a tertiary care hospital in North India. All of them underwent 3D-TVUSG and were given provisional diagnosis after that endometrial biopsy was done and final diagnosis was given as per histopathological reports.

Results: Mean age of study participants was 59.4+/-4.3. Endometrial carcinoma was detected in about one tenth (8.2%) of participants by 3D-TVUSG while only (6.5%) of participants were diagnosed by histopathology. The histopathological diagnosis was considered the gold standard for detection and accuracy. Sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive value of 3D-TVUSG were 100%, 98.2%, 80% and 100% respectively. Diagnostic accuracy of 3D-TVUSG was 98.3%.

Conclusion: Three-dimensional transvaginal ultrasound (3D-TVUSG) has high diagnostic accuracy, sensitivity and specificity for endometrial carcinoma among postmenopausal women. Postmenopausal women should be regularly screened for endometrial carcinoma with the help of 3D-TVUSG.

Keywords: Postmenopausal bleeding; Menopause; Three-dimensional transvaginal ultrasound; Endometrial carcinoma; Thickness.

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Introduction

Bleeding after menopause is termed as postmenopausal bleeding (PMB). Women who have gone through menopause and have endometrial cancer typically show symptoms of vaginal bleeding. Postmenopausal bleeding represents 5% of all gynecologic outpatient attendances. Endometrial carcinoma of menopausal women usually manifests with vaginal bleeding in 90% of cases. The majority of post-menopausal women who encounter vaginal bleeding do so as a result of atrophic changes in the vagina or endometrium. However, approximately 14% of patients with endometrial carcinoma may vary depending on their risk factors and age [1]. Various studies and standard textbooks have suggested that ET (Endometrial Thickness) < 5 mm, as measured by 3D-TVUSG in postmenopausal women having abnormal bleeding, is unlikely to indicate any serious endometrial pathology, such as endometrial cancer. Therefore, endometrial biopsy is considered unnecessary as a result. Postmenopausal bleeding necessitates

immediate and thorough assessment to rule out any endometrial issues or detect potential carcinoma. Women having suspected endometrial pathology was investigated initially with 3D-TVUSG and later with endometrial biopsy. [2]

The use of clinical ultrasound diagnostic technology has advanced, leading to an increased reliance on ultrasound as the main clinical method for diagnosing postmenopausal vaginal bleeding. This is because it is non-invasive and easy to use. The use of ultrasound extends to the visual examination of blood flow in the uterus, enabling accurate identification of any abnormalities. Furthermore, the Doppler ultrasound imaging technology is able to detect any anomaly in tiny blood vessels of the uterus, thereby improving the accuracy in the diagnosis. We set out with the aim to evaluate how well 3D-TVUSG can detect endometrial cancer. [3] Postmenopausal bleeding raises significant concerns because it is the main clinical sign of endometrial

carcinoma. Endometrial carcinoma is diagnosed in approximately 10 to 20% of women experiencing postmenopausal bleeding, underscoring the need for thorough investigations in all women to rule out malignancy.^[4]

Although studies have been conducted regarding the diagnostic value of 3D-TVUSG among postmenopausal women, most of them have inconsistent results and also from developed countries and there are not many studies from North India. Therefore, due to paucity of literature in India, this study was planned to assess the diagnostic value of 3D-TVUSG for endometrial carcinoma among postmenopausal women in North India.

Materials and Methods

This was a prospective observational study which was conducted in a tertiary care hospital in North India from January 2023 till August 2024. Complete enumeration of all postmenopausal women attending General OPD was done. A total of 75 postmenopausal women were approached to participate in the study, out of which 61 participants were finally enrolled in the study based on necessary inclusion and exclusion criteria. Inclusion criteria were women of age more than 40 years with more than one year of menopause without any history of long-term hormonal treatment. Women who had any significant medical or surgical history and those who did not give consent were excluded from the study.

Study tools

The researchers utilized a pre-made, pre-validated, partially organized survey. It included inquiries

about socio demographic traits, current illness history, previous medical history, general physical and systemic examination. Standard laboratory tests were conducted. Subsequently three-dimensional transvaginal ultrasound (3D-TVUSG) was done for all participants with appropriate technique in presence of female attendant and endometrial biopsy as standard test for comparison of endometrial carcinoma.

Data Collection

After permission taken from the institutional ethical committee, they were provided written information sheet before undergoing the examination. They were instructed to empty their bladders beforehand. The tip of the transducer was covered with a condom after application of a small amount of gel. To ease the insertion, a small amount of lubricant gel was used. The probe was gently inserted into the vagina while the participant was in a lithotomy position. A transvaginal 3D transducer with a frequency range of 3 to 9 MHz was utilized for imaging the endometrium in the sagittal plane. Morphological changes, such as irregularities in the endometrium, varied echo textures, focal thickening, and indistinct endometrial borders were noted. The presence of an endometrial halo (a hypoechoic area between the endometrium and inner myometrium) was also observed. Vascularity, as well as the resistive index (RI), pulsatility index (PI), and peak systolic velocity (PSV) were assessed using color Doppler imaging. Layers of endometrium were measured anteriorly and posteriorly.

Fig 1. Multi-planar view contains four separate planes: mid-sagittal (A), transverse (B), coronal (C) and reconstructed 3D image of the uterus (D). On 3D-TVUSG provisional diagnosis of endometrial carcinoma was given as

Polypoidal, heterogeneous hypoechoic thickening with internal vascularity, irregular margins, loss of endometrial-myometrial interface or endometrial halo with endometrial free fluid.

Case illustration

A 66-year-old female (P3L3) having complaints of intermittent vaginal bleeding for the last 2 years. History – menopause achieved before 20 years, last delivery before 33 years without any previous significant medical history.

Figure 12:- TAS (A) and TVS (B) shows thick heterogeneous hypoechoic endometrium with internal vascularity later on 3D-TVUSG (C) shown irregular margins, loss of endo-myometrial interface suggesting myometrial invasion, which was confirmed by histopathology as endometrial adenocarcinoma (D).

Data analysis

Data was analyzed using SPSS software version 23.0 after transporting the data from MS excel. Simple tables were used to show frequency distribution. Chi square test was used for cross tables and associated factors.

Results

Table 1: Distribution Age Group And Years Of Menopause Among The Study Participants. (N=61)

Age group (years)	Number	Percentage (%)
41-45	2	3.2
46-50	12	19.6
51-55	19	31.1
56-60	22	36
>60	6	9.8
Total	61	100
Number of years since menopause	No.	%
1-5	16	26.2
6-10	13	21.3
11-15	26	42.6
>15	6	9.8
Total	61	100

Mean age of study participants was 59.4+/-4.3 with the range of 44 to 73 years. Maximum of the study participants (36.0%) were in the age group of 56-60 years. Majority of them (42.6%) had attained menopause within the last 11 to 15 years.

Table 2: Distribution of study population based on history and investigation (n=61)

Postmenopausal bleeding	Number	Percentage (%)
Yes	41	67.2%
No	20	32.7%
Co-morbid disease		
Yes	19	31.1%
No	432	68.9%
Obesity		
Yes	24	39.3%
No	37	60.6%
Endometrial carcinoma by 3D-TVUSG		
Yes	5	8.2%
No	56	91.8%
Endometrial carcinoma by Histopathology		
Yes	4	6.5%
No	57	93.54%

About two third (67.2%) of study participants gave a history of postmenopausal bleeding. About one third (31.1%) of study participants had associated comorbid disease while about two fifths (39.3%) of them were obese. Endometrial carcinoma was detected in about one tenth (8.2%) of participants by 3D TVUSG while only (6.5%) of participants were diagnosed by histopathology. Majority of

participants had normal findings or had endometrial hyperplasia or polyp on both ultrasonography and histopathological examination. On analyzing associated factors with abnormal endometrium histopathology, significant association for factors like number of years since menopause, presence of comorbid condition and postmenopausal bleeding was present.

Table 3: Diagnostic sensitivity and accuracy analysis of 3D-TVUSG for endometrial carcinoma among study participants.

3D-TVUSG diagnosis of endometrial carcinoma	Histopathological diagnosis of endometrial carcinoma		
	Positive	Negative	Total
Positive	4	1	5
Negative	0	56	56
Total	4	57	61

The histopathological diagnosis was considered the gold standard for detection and accuracy. Sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive value of 3D TVS USG were 100%, 98.2%, 80% and 100% respectively. Diagnostic accuracy of 3D TVS USG was 98.3%

Discussion

The mean age of our study participants was 59.4±4.3 with age range between 44 to 73 years. In a similar study by Yasser IA et al [5] in 2016, it was found that the mean age was 62 years with an age range between 42 to 84 years. In the present study, about one third (31.1%) of study participants had associated comorbid disease while about two fifths (39.3%) of them were obese and both these factors were found to be significantly associated with abnormal endometrium histopathology report. Almost similar results regarding comorbid conditions were reported by Yasser IA et al [5] in 2016. Study by Gull B et al [6] in 2001, reported that comorbid conditions were more in participants with abnormal endometrial histopathology reports. No association was found between body mass index and endometrial disease in our study which was also reported in similar studies conducted by Guven MA et al [7] in 2004 and Vanden BT et al [8] in their study participants. Endometrial carcinoma was detected in about one tenth (8.2%) of our participants by 3D TVUSG while only (6.5%) of participants were diagnosed by histopathology. In a study by Opolskiene G et al [9] in 2009, about one fifth (21%) of participants were found to had malignant endometrium on 3D ultrasonography while in another study by Gredmark T et al [10], it was found that about 15% of participants had endometrial cancer on histopathological examination. This difference regarding incidence of endometrial cancer across various studies could be due to different study population and study settings. In the present study, factors like postmenopausal bleeding (PMB), years of menopause, and the presence of co morbid diseases were found to be significantly associated with histopathology of the endometrium. Gredmark T et al [10] in his study reported that incidence of postmenopausal bleeding decreases with increase in age of study participants while incidence of endometrial cancer increases. In our study, the sensitivity, specificity, positive and negative predictive value of 3D TVS USG were found to be 100%, 98.2%, 80% and 100% respectively while diagnostic accuracy of 3D-TVUSG was found to be 98.3%. In a similar study by Liu L et al [11] in 2022, the accuracy, sensitivity and specificity of 3D-TVUSG were found to be 97.27%, 77.78% and 80% respectively.

Response rate of our study was high. Secondly, standard protocols were followed for study implementation and for the data collection procedures. The present study consists of few

limitations as well. Small sample size is the first limitation of our study. The findings of our study can't be generalized to entire postmenopausal women across India as data from only one hospital was taken.

Conclusion

Three-dimensional transvaginal ultrasound (3D-TVUSG) has high diagnostic accuracy, sensitivity and specificity for endometrial carcinoma among postmenopausal women. 3D-TVUSG ultrasonography can be useful in screening of endometrial carcinoma among postmenopausal women and its accuracy increased after application of doppler values particularly in detection of pathological changes. Further multicentric studies should be planned to give more conclusive evidence which can be generalizable across all postmenopausal women in India.

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